

Factor Associated with Atopic Dermatitis and Allergic Rhinitis in Patients Attending in Tertiary Care Center Pauri, Uttarakhand, India: A Hospital Based Retrospective Study.

Ratan Singh¹, Pooja Sharma², Sumit Kumar³, Arjun Singh Doshad⁴, Ravindra Bisht⁵

¹Associate Professor, Department of Dermatology, VCSG GIMS & R Srinagar, Uttarakhand, India.

²Assistant professor, Department of Microbiology, VCSG GIMS & R Srinagar, Uttarakhand, India.

³Assistant professor, Department of Community Medicine, VCSG GIMS & R Srinagar, Uttarakhand, India.

⁴Assistant Professor, Department of ENT, VCSG GIMS & R Srinagar, Uttarakhand, India.

⁵ Professor, Department of ENT, VCSG GIMS & R Srinagar, Uttarakhand, India.

Received: 01-11-2021 / Revised: 29-11-2021 / Accepted: 23-12-2021

Corresponding author: Dr. Arjun Singh Doshad

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Objectives: This present study was to evaluate the various factors associated with atopic dermatitis and allergic rhinitis in patients attending in tertiary care center Pauri, Uttarakhand, India.

Methods: Random sampling methods was used for data collection. We adapted a questionnaire from the Korean version of the International Study of Asthma and Allergies in Childhood (ISAAC) Standard Questionnaire for children, and we were developed a self-developed questionnaire for adults. We were interviewed the patients about the general items such as age, gender, and type of residence, and details of allergic diseases such as allergic rhinitis, atopic dermatitis, and details of other factors likely to be associated with allergic diseases.

Results: A total of 200 cases were enrolled in this study. Among them, 75(37.5%) patients were of atopic dermatitis and 125(62.5%) cases were of allergic rhinitis. 108(54%) most of the patients were males. 128(64%) patients were belonged in <18 years of age. And 72(36%) were belonged in ≥18 years of age. 108(54%) cases were lived in normal house and 92(46%) were lived in apartment. 115(57.5%) patients had family history of allergy.

Conclusions: This present study concluded that allergic rhinitis was more condition as compared to atopic dermatitis in Garhwal region of Uttarakhand, India. Atopic dermatitis was commonly seen in female gender as compared to allergic rhinitis. Most common associated factor of atopic dermatitis was age <18 years, normal housing, family history of allergy and low socio-economic status. While, most common associated factor of allergic rhinitis was age ≥18 years, apartment, family history of allergy and high socio-economic status.

Keywords: Atopic dermatitis, Allergic rhinitis, age group, Socio-economic status

This is an Open Access article that uses a fund-ing model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Allergic diseases are considered to arise through complex interactions between genetic susceptibility and environmental exposures [1], so that temporal trends in prevalence are most likely to be explained by changes in environmental exposure, lifestyle, and living conditions [2]. Among such changes considered to contribute to trends in allergic disease prevalence are climate [3], urbanization [4], air pollution [5], cigarette smoke exposure, breastfeeding, and other behavioral and lifestyles factors [2].

Atopic dermatitis and allergic rhinitis are diseases that typically develop in childhood and should not be regarded as minor disorders but rather as chronic diseases that cause very unpleasant symptoms and affect the quality of life of the patients and their families. In addition, these illnesses generate important costs both directly (consumption of health care resources and drugs) and indirectly (reduction in parent work yield) [6]. Epidemiological studies have revealed important differences in the prevalence of allergic disorders among different countries, and even within single countries, as well as contradictory results in relation to the possible associated risk or protective factors [6].

The study revealed that over 20% of children are affected by AD in some countries, but that the prevalence varies greatly throughout the world. For the age group 6–7 years, data showed that the prevalence of AD ranged from 0.9% in India to 22.5% in Ecuador, with new data showing high values in Asia and Latin America. For the age group 13–14 years, data showed prevalence values ranging from 0.2% in China to 24.6% in Columbia. A prevalence over 15% was found in 4 of 9 regions studied including Africa, Latin America, Europe (1 center in Finland) and Oceania [7].

The ISAAC (International Study of Asthma and Allergies in Childhood) was created in

1991 with the aim of establishing and comparing the prevalence of allergic disorders in childhood and adolescence in different countries, and to explore their trend over time, thanks to the adoption of standardized methodology. For this purpose, the study used a questionnaire comprising simple questions in an attempt to homogenize the diagnostic criteria in the different parts of the world, thereby preventing the reported differences in prevalence from being attributable to methodological differences. Up until that time there were few multinational epidemiological studies on pediatric allergic diseases, and most were referred to asthma. This study was focused on atopic dermatitis and rhinitis [6]. Objectives of this present study was to evaluate the factors associated with atopic dermatitis and allergic rhinitis in patients attending in tertiary care center Pauri, Uttarakhand, India.

Materials & methods

This present study was conducted in Department of Dermatology with the collaboration of Department of ENT in VCSGGIMS & R Srinagar, Pauri, Uttarakhand, India during a period from January 2020 to December 2020. Entire subjects signed an informed consent approved by institutional ethical committee of VCSG GIMS & R was sought.

Methods:

Random sampling methods was used for data collection. We adapted a questionnaire from the Korean version of the International Study of Asthma and Allergies in Childhood (ISAAC) Standard Questionnaire for children, and we designed a self-developed questionnaire for adults. We also adopted information for a questionnaire for adults based on a previously published paper from a South Korean study that made use of questions similar to the ISAAC Standard Questionnaires [18]. We were interviewed

the patients about the general items such as age, gender, and type of residence, and details of allergic diseases such as allergic rhinitis, atopic dermatitis, and details of other factors likely to be associated with allergic diseases [19]. Questionnaires were administered by pertained interviewers. A total of 200 patients of atopic dermatitis and allergic rhinitis who attended in OPD of Dermatology and ENT were selected for this study.

Statistical analysis

Data was analysed by the use of simple statistical methods with the help of MS-

Office software. All data was tabulated and percentages were calculated.

Observations

A total of 200 cases were enrolled in this study. Among them, 75(37.5%) patients were of atopic dermatitis and 125(62.5%) cases were of allergic rhinitis. Out of 200 patients, 108(54%) most of the patients were males. 128(64%) patients were belonged in <18 years of age. And 72(36%) were belonged in ≥ 18 years of age. 108(54%) cases were lived in normal house and 92(46%) were lived in apartment. 115(57.5%) patients had family history of allergy.

Table 1: Factors associated with atopic dermatitis and allergic rhinitis.

Variables	Total (N=200)	Atopic dermatitis (N=75)	Allergic rhinitis (N=125)	Total (N=200)
Gender	Male	36(48%)	72(57.6%)	108(54%)
	Female	39(52%)	53(42.4%)	92(46%)
Age group	<18 years	42(56%)	86(68.8%)	128(64%)
	≥ 18 years	33(44%)	39(31.2%)	72(36%)
Housing type	Housing	54(72%)	84(67.2%)	108(54%)
	Apartment	21(28%)	41(32.8%)	92(46%)
Family history of allergy	Yes	39(52%)	76(60.8%)	115(57.5%)
	No	36(48%)	49(39.2%)	85(42.5%)
Socioeconomical status	Low	31(41.33%)	28(22.4%)	59(29.5%)
	Middle	27(36%)	30(24%)	57(28.5%)
	High	17(22.67%)	67(53.6%)	84(42%)

Out of 75 atopic dermatitis cases, 39(52%) patients were atopic dermatitis, 42(56%) cases were in age <18 years, 54(72%) patients were lived in normal housing and 39(52%) cases, family history of allergy and 31(41.33%) belonged from low socio-economic status.

Out of 125 cases of allergic rhinitis, 72(57.6%) cases were males, 86(68.8%) cases were belonged in age <18 years, 84(67.2%) patients were lived in normal housing and 115(57.5%) patients had family history of allergy and 84(42%) belonged from high socioeconomic status.

Discussions

Allergic diseases represent growing health and economic burdens worldwide [8], and have frequently been reported to impair quality of life and retard cognitive functions [9]. About 40% of the global population suffer from an allergic disorder, and of the many allergic diseases known, the most common are atopic dermatitis (AD), allergic rhinitis (AR), and asthma [10]. The common clinical features of AR include profuse watery rhinorrhea, sneezing, itchy nose, and congestion with occasional experiences of itchy conjunctiva, ears, and

throat [11]. On the other hand, AD is a chronic relapsing inflammatory skin disease accompanied by respiratory allergy, recurrent bacterial (impetigo), fungal (tinea), and viral (Herpes Simplex molluscum contagiosum) skin infections [12]. Interestingly, a recent systematic review indicated that patients with AD have increased risks of cardiovascular diseases, certain malignancies, autoimmune diseases, and neuropsychiatric diseases [13]. Furthermore, the coexistence of asthma, allergic rhinitis, and eczema gives rise to more severe and intense symptoms which may lead to a poor quality of life [14].

In this present study, out of 200 cases of allergy, 75(37.5%) patients had atopic dermatitis and 125(62.5%) patients had allergic rhinitis. Most of common factors associated with atopic dermatitis were 42(56%) age of <18 years, 54(72%) normal housing and 39(52%) family history of allergy. 31(41.33%) most of the cases of atopic dermatitis were belonged from low socio-economic status.

Two previous nationwide studies conducted in South Korea reported AR prevalence of 27% and 17.2 % [15,16]. In one of these previous nationwide studies, 31.2% of the study population suffered from AD [15], which is more than twice that encountered in the present study. This may have been because Pohang-Si is an industrial city and industrial pollutants might have influenced such rising prevalence. However, the prevalence of AR and AD found in the present study is in line with that observed in a nationwide Korean study. In fact, several studies conducted in developed countries have shown a higher prevalence of allergic diseases [14,18], and in another, urban areas were found to be more prone to allergic diseases [18], which supports the argument that industrialization is associated with the higher prevalence of allergic diseases. Views differ regarding whether age is a risk factor of allergic

diseases [19]. One study [20] demonstrated a weak relation between age and allergic diseases, whereas another study [21] found a positive association. In the present study, those aged ≥ 18 had higher odds for AD and AR, possibly because our subjects were more exposed to allergens because this population may be more ambulatory, socio-economically active and might encounter more chances of being exposed to allergens during work and travel compared to the lower age group population.

In this present study, most common associated factors of allergic rhinitis were 86(68.8%) of age <18 years, 84(67.2%) lived in normal housing and 115(57.5%) family history of allergy. 72(57.6%) Male gender was greatly associated with allergic rhinitis. Most cases 84(42%) of allergic rhinitis were belonged from high socioeconomic status.

A number of studies have demonstrated an association between family history of allergic disease and the occurrence of atopic diseases in offspring [22,23]. Genetic contributions to allergic disease were estimated to be greater than 50% in two studies, with a range of 36–79% genetically inherited [24,25]. Genetic susceptibility for allergic diseases has been well reported, suggesting the common and distinct genetic loci associated with these diseases [26]. We found that male gender was significantly associated with AR, which is consistent with the results of other studies [17,18], but contrary to the findings of Gough et al. [14]. However, in addition to exposure to the environmental allergens, sex-specific genetic effects might also have contributed to the gender differences in the occurrence of allergic diseases because there are underlying differences in the inflammatory pathways to different allergens between women and men [27,28].

Conclusions

This present study concluded that allergic rhinitis was more condition as compared to

atopic dermatitis in Garhwal region of Uttarakhand, India. Atopic dermatitis was commonly seen in female gender as compared to allergic rhinitis. Most common associated factor of atopic dermatitis was age <18 years, normal housing, family history of allergy and low socio-economic status. While, most common associated factor of allergic rhinitis was age \geq 18 years, apartment, family history of allergy and high socio-economic status.

References

1. Strina A, Barreto ML, Cooper PJ, Rodrigues LC. Risk factors for non-atopic asthma/wheeze in children and adolescents: a systematic review. *Emerg Themes Epidemiol.* 2014; 11: 5.
2. Barreto ML, Cunha SS, Alcantara-Neves N, Carvalho LP, Cruz AA, Stein RT, et al. Risk factors and immunological pathways for asthma and other allergic diseases in children: background and methodology of a longitudinal study in a large urban center in Northeastern Brazil (Salvador-SCAALA study). *BMC Pulm Med.* 2006; 6: 15.
3. Weiland SK, Huising A, Strachan DP, Rzehak P, Pearce N, ISAAC Phase One Study Group. Climate and the prevalence of symptoms of asthma, allergic rhinitis, and atopic eczema in children. *Occup Environ Med.* 2004; 61: 609–615.
4. Moncayo AL, Vaca M, Oviedo G, Erazo S, Quinzo I, Fiaccone RL, et al. Risk factors for atopic and non-atopic asthma in a rural area of Ecuador. *Thorax.* 2010; 65: 409–416.
5. Weinmayr G, Forastiere F, Weiland SK, Rzehak P, Abramidze T, Annesi-Maesano I, et al. international variation in prevalence of rhinitis and its relationship with sensitisation to perennial and seasonal allergens. *Eur Respir J.* 2008; 32: 1250–1261.
6. J. Torres-Borrego, A.B. Molina-Terán and C. Montes-Mendoza. Prevalence and associated factors of allergic rhinitis and atopic dermatitis in children. *Allergol Immunopathol* 2008;36(2):90-100.
7. Williams H, Burney PG, Pembroke AC, Hay RJ. The UK Working Party's diagnostic criteria for atopic dermatitis. *Br J Dermatol.* 1994; 131:406–416.
8. Tokura Y. Extrinsic and intrinsic types of atopic dermatitis. *J Dermatol Sci.* 2010;58: 1–7.
9. Andiappan AK, Puan KJ, Lee B, et al. Allergic airway diseases in a tropical urban environment are driven by dominant mono-specific sensitization against house dust mites. *Allergy.* 2014;69: 501–509.
10. Tosi Nelson DM. Prevalencia de sensibilización a alérgenos respiratorios en pacientes que acuden a consulta externa de alergología."Consultorios Monte Sinai", Cuenca, 2009–2011. Universidad del Azuay. 2011.
11. Odhiambo, J.A.; Williams, H.C.; Clayton, T.O.; Robertson, C.F.; Asher, M.I. Global variations in prevalence of eczema symptoms in children from isaac phase three. *J. Allergy Clin. Immunol.* 2009; 124: 1251–1258.
12. Zuberbier, T.; Lotvall, J.; Simoons, S.; Subramanian, S.V.; Church, M.K. Economic burden of inadequate management of allergic diseases in the european union: A ga(2) len review. *Allergy* 2014; 69: 1275–1279.
13. Long, A.; McFadden, C.; DeVine, D.; Chew, P.; Kupelnick, B.; Lau, J. Management of allergic and nonallergic rhinitis. *Evid. Rep. Technol. Assess.* 2002; 54: 1–6.
14. Dave, N.D.; Xiang, L.; Rehm, K.E.; Marshall, G.D., Jr. Stress and allergic diseases. *Immunol. Allergy Clin. N. Am.* 2011; 31: 55–68.
15. Leung, D.Y.; Jain, N.; Leo, H.L. New concepts in the pathogenesis of atopic dermatitis. *Curr. Opin. Immunol.* 2003; 15: 634–638.

16. Andersen, Y.M.F.; Egeberg, A.; Skov, L.; Thyssen, J.P. Comorbidities of atopic dermatitis: Beyond rhinitis and asthma. *Curr. Dermatol. Rep.* 2017; 6: 35–41.
17. Kenfuni, M. M. ., Gallouo, M. ., alafifi, mahmoud, Tsikambu, A. C. D., Alafifi, R. ., Moataz, A. ., Dakir, M. ., Debbagh, A. ., & Aboutaieb, R. . (2022). Pyonephrose : Risk factors, clinical, para-clinical and anatomopathological profile about 19 cases. *Journal of Medical Research and Health Sciences*, 5(2), 1770–1773. <https://doi.org/10.52845/JMRHS/2022-5-2-1>
18. Gough, H.; Grabenhenrich, L.; Reich, A.; Eckers, N.; Nitsche, O.; Schramm, D.; Beschorner, J.; Hoffmann, U.; Schuster, A.; Bauer, C.P.; et al. Allergic multimorbidity of asthma, rhinitis and eczema over 20 years in the german birth cohort mas. *Pediatr. Allergy Immunol.* 2015; 26: 431–437.
19. Rhee, C.S.; Wee, J.H.; Ahn, J.C.; Lee, W.H.; Tan, K.L.; Ahn, S.; Lee, J.H.; Lee, C.H.; Cho, Y.S.; Park, K.H.; et al. Prevalence, risk factors and comorbidities of allergic rhinitis in south korea: The fifth korea national health and nutrition examination survey. *Am. J. Rhinol. Allergy* 2014; 28: e107–e114.
20. An, S.Y.; Choi, H.G.; Kim, S.W.; Park, B.; Lee, J.S.; Jang, J.H.; Sung, M.W. Analysis of various risk factors predisposing subjects to allergic rhinitis. *Asian Pac. J. Allergy Immunol.* 2015; 33: 143–151.
21. Nishijima, H.; Suzuki, S.; Kondo, K.; Yamasoba, T.; Yanagimoto, S. Environmental factors associated with allergic rhinitis symptoms in japanese university students: A cross-sectional study. *Auris Nasus Larynx* 2018; 45: 1006–1013.
22. De Lusignan, S.; Correa, A.; Pebody, R.; Yonova, I.; Smith, G.; Byford, R.; Pathirannehelage, S.R.; McGee, C.; Elliot, A.J.; Hriskova, M.; et al. Incidence of lower respiratory tract infections and atopic conditions in boys and young male adults: Royal college of general practitioner’s research and surveillance centre annual report 2015–2016. *JMIR Public Health Surveill.* 2018; 4: e49.
23. Chang, W.S.; Kim, E.J.; Lim, Y.M.; Yoon, D.; Son, J.Y.; Park, J.W.; Hong, S.J.; Cho, S.H.; Lee, J.S. Age-related changes in immunological factors and their relevance in allergic disease development during childhood. *Allergy Asthma Immunol. Res.* 2016;8: 338–345.
24. Dharma, C.; Lefebvre, D.L.; Tran, M.M.; Lou, W.Y.W.; Subbarao, P.; Becker, A.B.; Mandhane, P.J.; Turvey, S.E.; Sears, M.R. Patterns of allergic sensitization and atopic dermatitis from 1 to 3 years: Effects on allergic diseases. *Clin. Exp. Allergy* 2018; 48:48–59.
25. Ho, C.L.; Chang, L.I.; Wu, W.F. The prevalence and risk factors of atopic dermatitis in 6–8 year-old first graders in taipei. *Pediatr. Neonatol.* 2019; 60:166–171.
26. Chiesa Fuxench, Z.C. Atopic dermatitis: Disease background and risk factors. *Adv. Exp. Med. Biol.* 2017;1027:11–19.
27. Lee, M.T.; Wu, C.C.; Ou, C.Y.; Chang, J.C.; Liu, C.A.; Wang, C.L.; Chuang, H.; Kuo, H.C.; Hsu, T.Y.; Chen, C.P.; et al. A prospective birth cohort study of different risk factors for development of allergic diseases in offspring of non-atopic parents. *Oncotarget* 2017; 8: 10858–10870.
28. Koppelman, G.H. Gene by environment interaction in asthma. *Curr. Allergy Asthma Rep.* 2006; 6:103–111.
29. Renz, H.; Conrad, M.; Brand, S.; Teich, R.; Garn, H.; Pfeifferle, P. Allergic diseases, gene–environment interactions. *Allergy* 2011, 66, 10–12.

30. Portelli, M.A.; Hodge, E.; Sayers, I. Genetic risk factors for the development of allergic disease identified by genome-wide association. *Clin. Exp. Allergy* 2015;45: 21–31.
31. Weiss, L.A.; Abney, M.; Cook, E.H., Jr.; Ober, C. Sex-specific genetic architecture of whole blood serotonin levels. *Am. J. Hum. Genet.* 2005;76 :33–41.